

Fabrication and characterization of ZnO Nanosheets based Force sensor

Zabih Ullah^{1*}

¹Government of Balochistan Colleges Higher & Technical Education Department.

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ABSTRACT

This research reports the fabrication of ZnO nanosheets based force sensor. The sensor is fabricated by hydrothermal growth of ZnO nano sheets on three different surfaces of Al, nano structured Al and AAO. The sensor is electrically analysed with its response to the applied force which has promising results of sensing with both nano structured Al-ZnO nano-sheets and anodic aluminium oxide (AAO) surface ZnO nano sheets. With nanostructured Al/ZnO nanosheets the sensor was analysed terms of resistance variation (decrease) when force is applied. With a force of 9.8 N there was 700 kΩ decrease in resistance. The AAO/ZnO nano sheets were used to fabricate the FET based force sensor. For fabrication of FET based force sensor the drain and source were made on the top surface of 2D ZnO nanosheets by sputtering Au. The AAO was used as insulating layer and the Al substrate was used as gate. This FET force sensor has good response with both gate voltage off and on. However with VGS on an increased amount of current in response of applied force was received. The fabricated FET force sensor was used sensing both impulse and continuous force with a good proportionality of IDS with applied force. With VGS=0V an applied impulse force of 1N, 2N, and 7N, there was an increase in IDS by 2.5, 3, 5.5 folds. Similarly with VGS=10V the applied force of 1N produces an increase of 10 folds in IDS. The sensor was also tested for continuous force where a step up response in IDS was observed. The ZnO nanosheets based sensors can find wide applications in various fields for force and pressure sensing and measurement.

Introduction

Nano technology has become one of the dominant fields of physics as it has opened the doors for many applications in almost every field. Nanotechnology has served as industrial production, automotive, medicines, indoor air control, gas sensing, environment control, health control and surgeries etc. [1]. It is the need of modern era to control the size of devices by miniaturization to increase its performance and reduce cost. The world needs to convert from the bulky

traditional power generating devices to the smart nanotechnology based self-powered devices. Because portable devices have gained much attention, self-powered portable devices will play a crucial role in the next generation advance technology-based devices. [2][3] For this purpose, various research articles are being published to use maximum amount of clean energy around us rather than the previously used Fossil fuel. With the help of nanotechnology, the researchers have fabricated several self-powered devices.

* Corresponding author. Zabih Ullah

E-mail address: khanzabiullah45@gmail.com

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These devices are powered by the ambient energy such as vibration, or human motion which is converted in electrical energy to power smart sensors or devices. Nanotechnology helps to design smart, mini, low cost, ambient energy-based devices [4]. Mechanical-energy is easily converted and abundant in our atmosphere. Mechanical energy can be obtained from all the motions present in atmosphere [5]. The ambient mechanical energy is unfortunately neglected in designing system and it is considered to be the drawback of such devices and systems. Wang et al reported that, this energy can be utilized for powering smart sensors and devices. For this purpose, the research work must focus on new and innovative designs of devices. These energy conversion devices will be able to convert maximum amount of mechanical energy into electrical energy [6].

The new and innovative designs and devices can be used for sensing purpose. Sensors play very essential role in the modern life. Sensors have eased the lives in all fields of life. Sensors are used in industries, house hold, traffic control, medication, weather forecast and predictions of the natural disasters such as Tsunami. [7] Sensor fabrication has also been utilized for atmospheric change control, medical field and harmful gases emitted from industries, factories and traffic. Sensors have been used to know about the cancer in the body after knowing the inhaling gas ratio of the Oxygen and exhaling carbon dioxide gas. In recent years, pollution has been a serious threat for naturally occurring atmosphere and causing a lot of diseases such as skin diseases, eye sight weakness etc. Research work has been focusing the growth of sensors for atmospheric changes. Different sensors have been fabricated for knowing the ratio of harmful gases and materials in the natural atmosphere. 2D and 3D nano structures have been reported with promising results in the field of sensing. [7-9]. Ambient power sensors can be made for different purposes such as human body implantation to detect different diseases and biological disorders in the human body. FET sensors have been playing a vital role in the field of sensing. Beginning from the pioneer work in 1975 for hydrogen gas sensing by Lundstrom et al. There is much research work on FET sensing ranging to capacitor based, Schottky diode based and catalytic gated based FET sensors. SiC based and catalytic-gate based high electron mobility transistors based FETs are also reported for high temperature and harsh conditions gas sensing of H, H₂, CO, C₂H₂ and NO₂. Furthermore, suspended gate and solid electrolyte and Nano material-based FETs have been reported. Nano material-based FETs are of high attention due to their large surface to volume ratio, fast response, recovery time and small dimensions.

For energy conversion and self-powered devices several types of nanomaterials are being used such as Carbon, ZnO, GaN, lead zirconate titanate (PTZ) etc. These materials are available in different structures including nano tubes, nano rods, nano dots, nano walls, nano sheets. Among those materials the ZnO has gained much attraction due to its easy fabrication process, durability, and low cost, self-cleansing, antibacterial behavior, skin compatibility. [10][11]. ZnO is

also favored due to its high stability, high band gap energy (3.34 eV), high exciton binding energy (60 meV), optical and electrical properties.[12] Variety of ZnO nanostructures have been fabricated including nanorods, nanospheres, nanodots, nanobelts, nanotubes, and nanosheets etc. [13][14][15]ZnO has been reported with UV screen blockers, cosmetics, fight against germs (micro-organism), antibacterial activities, drug delivery, designing of enzymes biosensors and immune sensors etc. ZnO nanorods and nano wires have also been reported with making of nano generators, UV sensors, Light emitting diodes and solar cells. [16], [17] Growth of ZnO nano structures has been reported with different methods. growth of ZnO nano structures with VLS method both tip growth and base growth has been reported by Dahia et al., 2014. The fabrication of ZnO nano rods and wires is reported with both vapor and liquid processes of growth. The vapor process is vapor solid (VS), Vapor solid-liquid (VLS) and also chemical vapor deposition (CVD). ZnO nano sheet growth by hydrothermal process has been reported by Aminullah et al and Sumera et al.,2020. The ZnO nanosheets due to its high flexibility, sensitivity and durability has better performance in energy harvesting and sensing applications as compare to other nanostructures.

ZnO is a good material for fabrication of sensors and energy harvesting devices. However, the available ZnO nanostructures such as nanorods, nanotubes, and nano spheres are difficult to integrate with electrodes to form sensors. Due to this limitation sensors are fabricated with low sensitivity, and durability. Research was needed to introduce new ZnO nanostructure which should have better connectivity in larger area [18-20]. ZnO nanosheets have a promising future for sensing applications. ZnO nanosheets based sensor could prove a big achievement in the field of nano technology-based sensing.

In this work we report the fabrication of mechanical sensor with ZnO nano sheets. The ZnO nanosheets was fabricated on different surfaces of Al and AAO. The AAO/ZnO sheets based device was used as FET force sensor.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The fabrication process of 2D ZnO NS based force sensor is shown in Figure 1. 99.999% pure Al sheet was cleaned ultrasonically in Acetone and DI water. The Al sheet was then electropolished in 1:4 v/v ratios of perchloric acid and ethanol at potential difference of 15 V by keeping the temperature from 0 to 5°C. For making AAO insulating layer on the top surface of Al the two steps anodization was performed in 0.3M oxalic acid at potential difference of 40V and keeping the temperature constant at 0°C. The first step of anodization was performed for 6h and 2nd step ranging from 20 min to 60 min depending the target thickness of AAO.

The 2D ZnO nanosheets network was grown on AAO surface using hydrothermal method. For the growth of ZnO nanosheets the ZnO seed layer was deposited on AAO/Al surface using sol gel method. The sol gel was prepared in two

steps. The first step was to mix 0.11 g of zinc acetate dehydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), with 50 ml of methanol at 60 °C. The second step was to mix 0.03 g of sodium hydroxide in 25 ml of methanol and dissolve at 60 °C. Finally, the sodium/methanol solution was mixed in zinc acetate/methanol solution drop by drop for 2h at 60 °C to have transparent sol-gel. The sol-gel was deposited on AAO/Al samples using dip coating and then annealing at 140°C. For hydrothermal growth the samples were then fitted into a floating chamber to float on the surface of the nutrient solution. The nutrient solution was prepared using 0.02M zinc nitrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and 0.02M HMTA. The growth process was performed at 85°C for 3h, 4h and 6h depending on the target thickness of 2D ZnO nanosheets.

For making source and drain a 100 nm Au layer was deposited on surface of 2D ZnO nanosheets and patterned using UV photo lithography technique.

For electrical analysis the electrodes were connected with source, drain and gate where the Al substrate serves as gate.

Figure 1: Fabrication of ZnO nano sheets'-based FET force sensor

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

The structural analysis of three samples were done with FE-SEM. Figure.2 shows the structural results. In the results it was confirmed that the ZnO nanosheets were grown on all three samples. The height of the sheets was directly proportional to the fabrication period. Results from FE-SEM confirm the growth of the ZnO nano sheets on Al, nano structured Al and AAO sample. This shows that the ZnO sheets formation is the result of incorporation of Al doping in ZnO and the role of nano porous structure is negligible. Impurity from Al or other impurities added from surrounding are the cause of formation of ZnO nano sheets. After the growth of ZnO nano sheets, the samples were gold sputtered to form electrodes. Figure 2 shows the channel of ZnO nano sheets in dark while the gold electrodes in light colour.

Figure 2: ZnO nano sheets-based force sensor

ELECTRICAL ANALYSIS

In this work sensors are fabricated with three different surfaces of Al i.e the electro polished Al surface, the nano structured Al surface and anodized Al oxide surface. The sensor formation process is discussed above in detail.

The sensor fabricated with electro polished Al surface did not show any promising results as the growth of ZnO was on Al surface and it was completely conducting with no variation of resistance and capacitance with applied force. The sensor showed a very positive response when Al was etched from back side in channel and connection of electrode was provided from Al surface. However, it was a very difficult task to etch only Al not the ZnO nano sheets. Therefore, electropolished Al surface is not a good candidate for force sensor fabrication until only Al etchant is found.

The second sample of nano structured Al-ZnO nano sheets resulted in very promising results of sensing both in terms of resistance variation and capacitance variation. The decrease in resistance was directly proportional to the applied force. The decrease in resistance is caused due to Piezo electric effect where an induced charge layer is found between the source and drain in the response of applied force. Resultantly the flow of charges becomes easy as they get a wide band for motion. nano structured Al-ZnO nano sheets-based sensor is very promising with the device response and ease of fabrication. Further it has a very rapid response to the applied force which confirms that the sheets formation is better with nano structured Al-ZnO. The resistance decrease with force finally reaches to its lowest value and there is no decrease in resistance any further by applying any other magnitude of force. Figure 3 illustrates the electrical response of the sensor to the applied force in the form of weight. This sensor shows high sensitivity with applied force. A decrease of 770 kΩ of resistance with a force of less than 4 N was observed. This results that the decrease of resistance with 1 kΩ requires a force about 5mN which still a high decrease is. Therefore, this device is a highly sensitive, robust, durable and cost-effective force sensor.

Figure 3: Electrical and capacitive response nano porous Al ZnO nano sheets sensor

The third sample was ZnO nano sheets grown on anodic Al oxide surface. The fabrication of this sample requires two steps of anodization and electrodes can be provided with two top surfaces of Au grown on ZnO nano sheets and one electrode connection can be provided from Al surface. In between the top and bottom electrodes there is thin insulating layer of AAO. This makes the sample capable of FET response. Therefore, this sample can be used as FET which can be both gate voltage control sensor and also force sensor. The sensing capability can be enhanced with use of both gate voltage and force.

Figure 4. ZnO FET gate voltage response

Figure 4 shows the plot between VGS and IDS in forward and reverse direction that is providing positive and negative voltage at gate and changing the polarity of VDS as well. With positive gate voltage the positive charges accumulate near the surface which results to induce a conductive channel between source and drain. The conductivity of this induced channel is directly proportional to the gate voltage. The maximum IDS of 35 μA was recorded at 300V of VGS. Similarly, the with negative gate voltage the negative charge carriers were accumulated at the surface of nanosheets making an induced conductive channel between source and drain where the channel conductivity was directly proportional the applied VGS. The maximum IDS of 38 μA was recorded at -250V of VGS. By further increasing the gate voltage a breakdown was recorded where the IDS reduced rapidly. The FET behavior of device is very clear from the transfer characteristic as shown in figure 4. After

confirmation of FET response, the device was checked by applying force on the top surface for exposed channel. The device was configured by giving 10V VGS and 2V VDS. An impulse force was applied and variation in the IDS was recorded as shown in figure 5. The impulse response can be seen clearly in the variation of IDS. The IDS was increased by 12.5 times by applying force however the recovery time of IDS is slower. After removal of force it takes around 3 second to reach the previous value of current. By applying force due to piezoelectric effect, the negative charge increases on the top of nanosheets which results in increased conductivity between source and drain. The piezoelectric response is very different from the effect as observed from top to bottom in case of piezoelectric nanogenerators. Here the nanosheets are connected with each other horizontally and the applied force produces negative charge at top surface where it results in making conductive channel between sources to drain. As the force is removed the top surface again neutralized and the resistance from source to drain increases.

Figure 5. Applied force response of FET sensor

Figure 6: VDS versus IDS by applying force.

Figure 6 shows the response of the sensor with applied force of 1 N, with VDS varying from 0-2 V and VGS = 0V. In the graph a rapid increase in IDS is shown at VDS=1.2V where the force was applied on the sensor. After applying force

there is increase in IDS which is directly proportional to applied VDS. The IDS is increased by 5 folds by applying a force of 1 N. In this case the continuous force is applied instead of impulse force.

Figure 7: Applied force response of FET with VGS open and Constant VDS

Figure 7 confirms highly sensitive response of the sensor with VGS = 0V (off) and constant VDS of 2V. Impulse force is applied at different instants with different magnitude. With applied impulse force of 1N, 2N, and 7N, there is increase IDS by 2.5, 3, 5.5 folds. There is also the decrease of current from original position after impulse response which may be due to harmonics in restoration of 2D-nanosheets generating piezoelectric effect. From figure 5, 6 and 7 it is very clear that the fabricated sensor can sense the impulse and continuous force with a good proportionality of IDS with applied force. This sensor is working in both VGS off and on mode. However, by applying the VGS comparatively an increases value of IDS is achieved which makes it a good candidate for using in consumer products which using any extra stage for amplification

CONCLUSION

In summary of the article, we fabricated ZnO nano sheets on three samples with low temperature hydrothermal growth. The ZnO nano sheets grown on the Al sample could not be used as a sensor as it is conducting on the Al surface, and there is no etchant known to us which could etch only Al with and protect ZnO nano sheets. The second sample with ZnO nano sheets grown on nano structured Al surface showed highly sensitive response to applied force. The response was in the form of resistance decrease. This sample response with 9.8 N weight was the decrease of almost 700 kΩ. Third sample was the growth of ZnO nano sheets on AAO surface. The advantage of this sample is that it can be used as an FET sensor with high sensitivity and durability. The drain and source were made on the top surface of 2D ZnO nanosheets by sputtering Au. The AAO was used as insulating layer and the Al substrate was used as gate. This

FET force sensor has good response with both gate voltage off and on. However, with VGS on an increased amount of current in response of applied force was received. From this research it is very clear that the fabricated sensor can sense the impulse and continuous force with a good proportionality of IDS with applied force. With VGS=0V an applied impulse force of 1N, 2N, and 7N, there is increase in IDS by 2.5, 3, 5.5 folds. Similarly, with VGS=10V the applied force of 1N produces an increase of 10 folds in IDS. The sensor was also tested for continuous force where a step up response in IDS was observed. The fabricated sensor is low cost and highly sensitive to force response. Such a sensor can be used in consumer sensing devices without using any extra circuit for amplification.

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REFERENCES

1. Bhatia, S., Verma, N., & Bedi, R. K. (2017). Ethanol gas sensor based upon ZnO nanoparticles prepared by different techniques. *Results in physics*, 7, 801-806.
2. Chang, X., Sun, S., Sun, S., Liu, T., Xiong, X., Lei, Y., ... & Yin, Y. (2018). ZnO nanorods/carbon black-based flexible strain sensor for detecting human motions. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 738, 111-117.
3. Condello, M., De Berardis, B., Ammendolia, M. G., Barone, F., Condello, G., Degan, P., & Meschini, S. (2016). ZnO nanoparticle tracking from uptake to genotoxic damage in human colon carcinoma cells. *Toxicology in Vitro*, 35, 169-179.
4. Gottam, S. R., Tsai, C. T., Li, C. Y., & Chu, S. Y. (2020). Investigation of MoS2 Nanosheet-Coated ZnO Thin Films for Hydrogen Gas Sensing Applications and the Effect of Temperature on the Enhanced Sensor Response. *Journal of The Electrochemical Society*, 167(8), 087507.
5. Kasi, A. K., Kasi, J. K., Uddin, M., & Bokhari, M. (2020). Triboelectric nanogenerator as self-powered impact force sensor for falling object. *Current Applied Physics*, 20(1), 137-144.
6. Kasi, A. K., Najma, B., Kasi, J. K., Rafique, S., & Bokhari, M. (2020). Fabrication of piezoelectric nanogenerator using 3D-ZnO nanosheets and optimization of charge storage system. *Materials Research Bulletin*, 123, 110711.
7. Kaur, M., Kailas Ganapathi, S., Ramgir, N., Datta, N., Kumar, S., Debnath, A. K., ... & Gupta, S. K. (2017).

- Gas dependent sensing mechanism in ZnO nanobelt sensor. *Applied Surface Science*, 394, 258-266.
8. Kim, K. H., Kumar, B., Lee, K. Y., Park, H. K., Lee, J. H., Lee, H. H., ... & Kim, S. W. (2013). Piezoelectric two-dimensional nanosheets/anionic layer heterojunction for efficient direct current power generation. *Scientific reports*, 3(1), 1-6.
 9. Leonardi, S. G. (2017). Two-dimensional zinc oxide nanostructures for gas sensor applications. *Chemosensory*, 5(2), 17.
 10. Lu, X., Zhang, H., Ni, Y., Zhang, Q., & Chen, J. (2008). Porous nanosheet-based ZnO microspheres for the construction of direct electrochemical biosensors. *Biosensors and bioelectronics*, 24(1), 93-98.
 11. Najma, B., Kasi, A. K., Kasi, J. K., Akbar, A., Bokhari, S. M. A., & Store, I. R. (2018). ZnO/AAO photocatalytic membranes for efficient water disinfection: Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial assay. *Applied Surface Science*, 448, 104-114.
 12. Rafique, S., Kasi, A. K., Kasi, J. K., Aminullah, Bokhari, M., & Shakoor, Z. (2020). Fabrication of silver-doped zinc oxide nanorods piezoelectric nanogenerator on cotton fabric to utilize and optimize the charging system. *Nanomaterials and Nanotechnology*, 10, 1847980419895741.
 13. Rafique, S., Kasi, A. K., Kasi, J. K., Bokhari, M., & Shakoor, Z. Fabrication of Br doped ZnO nanosheets piezoelectric nanogenerator for pressure and position sensing applications. *Current Applied Physics*, 21, 72-79.
 14. Sahdev, P., Podaralla, S., Kaushik, R. S., & Perumal, O. (2013). Calcium phosphate nanoparticles for transcutaneous vaccine delivery. *Journal of biomedical nanotechnology*, 9(1), 132-141.
 15. Shao, S., Chen, X., Chen, Y., Zhang, L., Kim, H. W., & Kim, S. S. (2020). ZnO Nanosheets Modified with Graphene Quantum Dots and SnO₂ Quantum Nanoparticles for Room-Temperature H₂S Sensing. *ACS Applied Nano Materials*.
 16. Shetti, N. P., Bukkitgar, S. D., Reddy, K. R., Reddy, C. V., & Aminabhavi, T. M. (2019). ZnO-based nanostructured electrodes for electrochemical sensors and biosensors in biomedical applications. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 141, 111417.
 17. Shetti, N. P., Bukkitgar, S. D., Reddy, K. R., Reddy, C. V., & Aminabhavi, T. M. (2019). ZnO-based nanostructured electrodes for electrochemical sensors and biosensors in biomedical applications. *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 141, 111417.
 18. Wang, L., Liu, S., Zhang, Z., Feng, X., Zhu, L., Guo, H., ... & Wang, Z. L. (2019). 2D piezotronics in atomically thin zinc oxide sheets: Interfacing gating and channel width gating. *Nano Energy*, 60, 724-733.
 19. Wang, Q., Yang, D., Qiu, Y., Zhang, X., Song, W., & Hu, L. (2018). Two-dimensional ZnO nanosheets grown on flexible ITO/PET substrate for self-powered energy-harvesting nanodevices. *Applied Physics Letters*, 112(6), 063906. Wei, A., Pan, L., & Huang, W. (2011). Recent progress in the ZnO nanostructure-based sensors. *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, 176(18), 1409-1421.
 20. Zhu, L., & Zeng, W. (2017). Room-temperature gas sensing of ZnO-based gas sensor: A review. *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, 267, 242-261.

